

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING THE PERSPECTIVE ON THE BASIS OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH WITH OTHER DISCIPLINES

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Annotation:

This article discusses the methodological system for the formation of geometric graphic abilities of students of technical higher educational institutions, the fact that graphics are of leading importance in the work of operators of complex systems that represent information in graphic forms.

Keywords: integration, perspective, image, verticality, Graphics, Design.

In the development of aesthetic taste and culture of a person, as well as in the cultivation of his spiritual worldview, fine art has its place. The created works of fine art reflect philosophical thought, a sense of consent from time or its reflection, enjoyment of the beauty of nature and other psychological situations. The artist expresses his opinion, his attitude towards society, the environment and the world through lines, shapes, colors. And art critics convey the artist's opinion to the audience, art lovers, in general to the people in a written or oral way.

As Danny Didro said, " Which nation diligently teaches drawing to its children, as if teaching letters, reading and counting, this nation will surpass other nations in science, culture and art." For this reason, in many developed countries, great attention is paid to fine arts, and it is taught as a separate subject in educational institutions, especially in general secondary schools. An example of this is the Japanese state, which perfectly teaches the fine arts to the younger generation. As we all know, Japan is a country developed in terms of economic

and glorifying its history. In our independent country, the science of Fine Arts is also taught in grades 1-7 of general secondary schools.

Just as each subject has an “alphabet” of teaching and learning to the student, the science of Fine Arts has its own teaching methodology, laws on how to draw a picture correctly and convincingly. Only if the item in the executed image resembles its original, its vitality is ensured.

A bright manifestation of the Renaissance, Leonardo da Vinci (1452-1519), having mastered all the information formed about the perspective, developed it with both unique and extremely new ideas. This great figure wrote that “perspective is the root of Fine Art.”

Another Italian architect and artist, decorator Andrea del Patsson (1642-1709), the work “elegant artists and the perspective of architecture”, was published in Rome in 1693, where final conclusions were made on all types of perspective.

Russian artists of the XVII-XVIII centuries well mastered the theory of perspective and effectively used it. The first Russian professor of the Academy of artists A.P.Losenko (1737-1773) required his students to know human anatomy and perspective.

Famous Russian artist A.G.Venetsiyanov (1780-1847) argued that without scientific knowledge and laws of perspective, an artist could not create a worthwhile work.

Russian pedagogue-artist N.N.Ge (1831-1894) wrote that perspective cannot be distinguished from painting, that it must be known by every artist, that painting should not be done in reverse, such as first drawing and then correcting it by the perspective rule, and that perspective should be a traveling star in the work of artists.

From scientists from Uzbekistan R.X.Khorunov's textbook “drawing geometry” in 1961 (the second edition was published in 1964) also provided a place for the

perspective Department. It covers the theoretical foundations of perspective.

Professor Sh.K.Textbook “drawing geometry course” (1988 - th year), created by a group of authors led by Muradov.) Department of perspective Associate Professor P.Written by Adilov.

After gaining independence, the role of perspective science in the construction of a vivid image, the possibilities of making images in analytical methods, aspects related to the Fine Arts Associate Professor A.Valiyev's textbook” Perspektiva " (2009 - th.) and in textbooks (2012-y.) detailed coverage is given.

Despite the fact that there are so many scientific bases, educational literature presented above, not only school textbooks, but also educational literature related to the fine arts of vocational education and higher educational institutions do not show the rules of perspective used in drawing. That is, the artist (or artist-pedagogue) could not show the practical significance of perspective image construction methods in the textbooks and teaching aids they wrote.

If a work of Fine Art is created without following these rules, knowledgeable observers say “there is no perspective on this picture”, while ordinary observers say that “things in this picture are not like themselves.” The science of perspective acts as a scientific resource for creating a realistic picture and helps to describe things in such a structure as we see them with our eyes .

We want to think about the rules of perspective, which in this scientific article should be shown at least in the textbooks of the “Fine Arts” of general secondary schools, and which students are obliged to know.

For readers, we must say that initially, the continuation of parallel straight lines seems to our eyes to meet in Infinity, and if they are in a horizontal position, they meet on the horizon line. But if this meeting (intersection) point goes beyond the paper limit (figure 2.2.2, a), you will have to perform additional geometric builds. These constructions (rules of perspective) are fully explained to the reader once in

a step-by-step way, he will remember it for a lifetime.

For example, let's get acquainted with the correct execution of the drawing of the parallelepiped. First of all, the vertical AB and horizontal AC and AD sides of the parallelepiped are drawn taking as correct (figure 2.2.2, B).

2.2.2-rasm

To determine the horizontal BE edge of ABEC Yak, 1 point is marked on the horizon line, and A1, B1 straight lines are formed (figure 2.2.2, C). Passing a line parallel to the horizon line from Point C, the point of its intersection with A1 is determined by 2, and a vertical line is transferred from it. The transferred vertical line B1 cuts the segment at 3 points, and from this point a parallel (horizontal) line is transferred to C2. This line intersects with a vertical straight line removed from Point C, giving the point E in search, and a perspective of ABEC Yak is formed.

The perspective of ABFD Yak is also built just like ABEC Yak, and this process is understandable from the drawing (figure 2.2.2, d). In this way, the perspective of the parallelepiped will be done correctly (figure 2.2.2, e). That is, the cross-section of the parallelepiped at the horizon line of the AC and BE, as well as the horizontal edges AD and BF are provided. This perspective is the method of triangles in image execution.

There is also a rectangular method. Figure 2.2.3 shows in orthogonal projection that ABEC is divided into two rectangles of a straight rectangle and that the line connecting the intersection points of its diagonals is vertical.

Figure 2.2.4 shows the correct execution of the picture (perspective) of the parallelepiped in the rectangular method. To do this, a horizon line is passed as above, and the vertical AB, horizontal AC and AD edges of the parallelepiped are perceived as straight.

Using the rule shown in Figure 2.2.3, the horizontal be edge of the parallelepiped is determined. To do this, points 1 and 2 are marked, intersecting with the horizon line of vertical lines subtracted from point A and C. Diagonals A2 and C1 are transferred, the point of their intersection is determined by 3. The vertical line removed from 3 points B2 cuts the diagonal and gives 4 points. Then points 1 and 4 are adjacent and point E is determined, intersecting it with a vertical line removed from Point C. BE cut will be the horizontal edge of the parallelepiped (figure 2.2.4, a).

2.2.4-rasm

The perpetual of the Abed collar of the parallelepiped is also built as if it were ABEC noq (figure 2.2.4, B). The result is that the picture (perspective) of the parallelepiped is done correctly (figure 2.2.4, C).

Geometric constructions (perspective rules) in pictures 2.2.2 and 2.2.4 can be performed even without the use of drawing tools, and this should be shown to

students by the teacher in practical terms.

In the examples we considered, the upper base of the parallelepiped was not visible to the Observer. If the upper base of the parallelepiped is located below the horizon line, its upper base is visible to the Observer. In this case, it is necessary to build the perspective of the upper base of the parallelepiped. In this, too, the method of triangles can be used.

Figure 5 shows the Observer step by step the process of performing a picture (perspective) of a parallelepiped to which the upper base is visible. The acceptance of the ab , AC , AD edges of the parallelepiped as correct, the perspective of the BE and BF edges of the upper base is determined as in Figure 2.2.2 and 2.2.4 (figure 2.2.5, a and b).

To determine the direction of the FN edge on the upper base, an optional point 1 is marked on the horizon line, and it is adjacent to points F and B (Figure 5, C). Then a straight line parallel to line $B1$ is transferred from point E and point 2 is found on the horizon line. Then, from point E , the intersection point 3 of the straight lines transferred parallel to points BF and $1F$ from Point 2 is determined. A straight line connecting points F and 3 FN will be the direction of the edge.

To determine the direction of the edge on the upper base, an optional point 4 is marked on the horizon line, and it is adjacent to points E and B (fig. Then a straight line parallel to line $B4$ is transferred from point F , intersecting with its horizon line, where Point 5 is found. Then point F is determined by the intersection point 6 of the straight lines, which are transferred from point BE and 5 points parallel to $4E$ s. A straight line connecting points E and 6 will be the direction of the en edge. Straight lines $F3$ and $E6$ intersect, giving Point N , and a perspective of the $BENF$ upper base of the parallelepiped is formed (figure 2.2.5, e).

2.2.5-rasm

If the upper base of the parallelepiped remains closer to the horizon line, it will be convenient if the diagonals of its collars are used when applying the method of triangles. Figure 6 shows the execution of the perspective of the upper base of the parallelepiped using its diagonals.

To determine the direction of the FN edge of the upper base, the AF diagonal of the ABFD collar is performed. From Point C to AF, straight lines made parallel to point E to point BF intersect at Point 1. F1 straight line FN will be the direction of the edge (figure 2.2.6, a).

And to determine the direction of the en edge of the upper base, the Ae diagonal of ABEC Yok is performed. Straight lines running from point D to Ae

and from point F parallel to be intersect at 2 points. E2 will be the direction of the straight line EN edge (figure 2.2.6, B). Straight lines F1 and E2 intersect, giving Point N, and the upper base of the parallelepiped is formed BENF (Figure 6, C).

Drawing based on the rules of perspective presented above gives the opportunity to achieve the correct execution of the image of objects as in the pictures shown below (figure 2.2.7).

a)

b)

c)

The role and practical significance of perspective rules in ensuring uniformity and similarity between the object in the image and its real appearance in life is enormous. This should never be forgotten. Hence, bringing complementary aspects of the visual arts and perspective disciplines into education, ensuring the mutual integration of the two disciplines is an urgent issue of today.

The rules of perspective in the methodological recommendations proposed by us are presented as a model in school textbooks of Fine Arts, shown by a widowed teacher in a practical way, and as a result of the students ' use in the lessons, the correct implementation of the drawing is achieved. If the reader independently once or twice applies these rules to drawing, this will be remembered by him all his life. This results in the viability of the painting the reader is drawing, and, as the great artist Moni said, “ ... only if anyone can give life to every line in the image will he have occupied the key to art.”

In the graphics in school textbooks, the means of expression, the means of expression of the art of Design,

today it is impossible to imagine any sphere of our life, including the educational system, without information technology, as well as computers, which are its basis. We can see examples of diverse design art in the technical direction. When describing the phased pencil drawing of a naturmort made of geometric shapes, in the process of observation, study of being, representation of volumetric objects on a paper surface, concepts and representations about the spatial state are formed.

In addition, the stages of drawing still lifes in school textbooks, working on a themed Still Life made from national dishes, depicting a tree on a clear night or at the sunset, working on a composition on the topic "Binocurity" work on the method of graphic and sculpting the body of a person in motion, an athlete, working on a landscape genre in fine On such topics as architectural monuments of Uzbekistan, making and decorating a building layout in a collective way, we can also see the perspective science of fine art directly.

Color perspective. To understand the color perspective, it is important that we all have a general understanding of the term perspective. When looking at perspective and painting, it means reflecting our 3D world on a 2D surface (paper or canvas). So it's about having objects larger than objects at a distance in the foreground.

If you want your image to be seen by the viewer in its depth, the color perspective is very important. Shades, tones and heat of color the main rule that must be followed by this type of point of view is that the nearest objects will have the darkest shades in the foreground. This photo perfectly describes the rule: the darkest tones of the "Blue" Sea are in the foreground. As the sea moves away ... depending on the horizon, the tones turn pale.

A great way to check if your Tonal values (i.e. your color perspective) are correct is to squint when you look at your work.

This image relies entirely on tone values and color perspective to create a sense of depth. Without the dark tones of the previous background or the Dimest tones in the distance, we cannot feel the perspective and depth in this landscape.

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